

Extensible FRER Security Testbed in a Box

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Abstract—Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) is expected to provide reliable, low-latency communication for critical systems. Leveraging the Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) protocol, it protects against packet loss by replicating individual packets and delivering them on disjoint forwarding paths. FRER does not contain any in-built security solutions, and several FRER-related security vulnerabilities have recently been identified that could undermine TSN’s ultimate goal of providing extreme reliability. In this paper, we introduce a comprehensive security-focused testbed for analyzing FRER vulnerabilities. Our self-contained setup employs open and adaptable components, runnable on a single server, ensuring flexibility and accessibility. Leveraging eBPF/XDP, it efficiently implements FRER’s data plane functionalities, accommodating both fast-path and slow-path attacks. Parameters like delay, jitter, loss rate, and bandwidth are easily customizable. We validate the testbed’s effectiveness with various attack scenarios.

Index Terms—TSN, FRER, security, testing

I. INTRODUCTION

The industry has developed numerous industrial protocols over the decades to support manufacturing automation. While these protocols serve well for point-to-point communication, integrating them into larger systems or new transport channels, like radio transmission, requires unification. This need led to TSN, envisioned as a universal industrial protocol catering to various use cases, from fieldbus applications to command and control interfaces.

TSN was chosen as the universal industrial protocol for 3GPP 5G networks starting from Release 16, implemented as Time Sensitive Communication (TSC) in 3GPP. While adoption is still in early stages, TSN-enabled devices are available, and efforts are underway to standardize its usage. Extensions like Deterministic Networking (DetNet) for Layer 3 time-synchronized communication and integrating OPC UA with TSN are in development, promoting adoption further.

Recent papers have collected and implemented basic attack types on TSN [1]. While these attacks were successful in terms of functionality, they had limited impact due to the hardware and software components used. In this paper, we propose a testbed framework in which the attacks can be implemented in Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF)/eXpress Data Path (XDP) and thus can achieve high speed and can potentially be offloaded to smartNICs resulting in line-rate performance. Given the importance of testing, we provide the test environment as an open-source contribution¹, extending the

work of [2]. Furthermore, we provide measurements to assess the increased impact of the attacks with our extension compared to the baseline case.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces FRER and discusses the need for the exploration of its security aspects. Section III describes some known attack types against FRER. Section IV describes the requirements for an ideal testbed and the technical details how we met these requirements. In Section V we describe the experiments we carried out throughout our work and discuss the results we produced. Section VI discusses the related work Section VII draws the conclusion for our paper.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The IEEE 802.1CB FRER protocol, detailed in [3], aims to reduce packet loss by replicating data packets across redundant paths. It employs maximally disjoint forwarding paths to minimize convergence effects. Replication duplicates packets across paths with a sequence number in an FRER header, while Elimination discards redundant packets sharing the same sequence number. Our FRER implementation, based on [3], encodes additional information called Redundancy Tag (R-TAG) into Ethernet frames, comprising EtherType, Reserved, and Sequence number fields for frame identification.

The FRER protocol does not have any built-in security mechanism and thus its two main functions, replication and elimination, are open to particular threats. Some challenges on ensuring reliability have already been addressed, e.g., in [4], [5]. The authors of [6] have identified several vulnerabilities for Packet Replication and Elimination in deterministic networking that also hold for the FRER protocol.

In summary, it is crucial to conduct a comprehensive examination of potential exploitation methods and approaches for detecting and mitigating malicious activities associated with FRER, given its lack of widely accepted security measures and prevalent use in mission-critical systems.

III. FRER ATTACKS

A. Sequence number modification attacks

The elimination of redundant frames occurs entirely based on the sequence number. If an attacker manipulates or modifies sequence numbers, they can disrupt the Elimination function and receiver. Without integrity checks higher in the network stack, attackers can increment sequence numbers on select links, causing duplicate data sequences and loss. Even with

¹Source code: https://github.com/kkaroly42/frer_security_testbed

integrity checks, attackers can still modify sequence numbers to cause data loss, constituting a denial of service attack.

B. Packet injection

We need to consider the cases in which the attacker does not have the ability to alter the packets traveling through the network, but does have the ability to inspect them and send out packets on its own. Here, a well timed packet with the following correct sequence number will be accepted by the Elimination function and get passed to the receiver.

As noted in [7], if the attacker sends packets with existing sequence numbers later than genuine packets, it triggers a latent error signal in the Latent Error Detection function, described in [3]. This signal alerts upper layers to a potential error condition, leading to uncertainty about data integrity and requiring costly precautions.

C. Path manipulation

In [7], authors discuss path manipulation attacks against FRER, highlighting the protocol's lack of path configuration or validation. This raises security concerns as attackers could manipulate forwarding logic in network devices. If attackers reroute redundant FRER packets intended for different links, it compromises redundancy, strains targeted links, and increases the potential for data loss.

IV. TESTBED DESIGN

In this section, we briefly introduce the testbed design we created for the analysis of various attacks against FRER communication channels.

A. Selection of FRER implementation

First, we formulated four **requirements** against the proposed testbed environment:

- 1) It should be lightweight so anyone can run it without the need for a special equipment.
- 2) It should be easily portable to a real environment when performance measurements on real hardware become necessary.
- 3) It should be easily extensible and could be customized since one can never exactly predict the direction the state of the art will take in the future.
- 4) The usage of the testbed should require as little specialized knowledge as possible, in order to keep the entry barrier low.

To satisfy the above requirements, we first had to make a decision on the FRER implementation to be used in our testbed. We found that the work presented in [2] is an ideal candidate to serve as the FRER stack in our environment. This open source implementation utilizes eBPF/XDP. eBPF [8] provides a safe way to extend the Linux kernel's functionality. Before loading the eBPF code, a verifier checks that the program is memory-safe and terminates. XDP [9] is a type of eBPF program that is called for every incoming packet. Its main advantage is that it runs before the packet enters the Linux networking stack, thus providing performance benefits.

Making use of the capabilities provided by XDP/eBPF the implementation presented in [2] can efficiently run even on a simple laptop without the need for special hardware (Requirement 1). For the same reason, the eBPF/XDP code can also be run in a real environment with very few modifications (Requirement 2).

Since the original implementation is entirely open-source and well-presented in [2], we argue that it also satisfies the extensibility requirements (Requirement 3). Additionally, its relatively small complexity (i.e., few hundreds lines of code) allows for quick understanding, and its capability to run in an unconstrained environment further supports this assertion.

Finally, since the implementation utilizes eBPF/XDP and Linux networking features, one can argue that Requirement 4 is satisfied as well. We acknowledge that mastering the mentioned topics can be challenging, but we believe it is fair to say that they are more commonplace than technologies used exclusively in specific research areas.

B. Testbed environment on a single server

Similarly to [2], we created a virtual network setup depicted in Fig. 1 where the two end-points (Talker and Listener) and the FRER segment with Replication, Elimination functions and the emulated channels are placed in isolated network namespaces. Namespace *Talker* is connected to namespace *FRERENV* via a Virtual Ethernet (veth) pair. The extended eBPF/XDP implementation runs inside *FRERENV*, realizing both Replication, Elimination functions and the extensible malicious addition function. The Replication function receives all the packets coming from namespace *Talker* and clone (broadcast) the each packet to all the FRER channels. In the figure, we only have two FRER channels, but the system can handle multiple channels. Each channel is emulated by a veth pair, representing a virtual Ethernet link. The link properties including loss rate, propagation delay, jitter and bandwidth are set by the well-known Linux tool *tc* (more precisely *tc netem*). The channel properties can easily be modified from configuration. After crossing the virtual links, packets are processed by the Elimination function that drop duplicates and forward a single instance of each packet to *Listener* via the veth pair interconnecting the two namespaces.

One can observe that the eBPF/XDP Malicious addition can be used to emulate an attacker who has the resources to make changes in every packet traveling through one of the FRER channels on the fast path. However, the flexibility of this fast path approach is limited as some complex operations are simply not allowed in eBPF. To bypass this limitation we also provide a more flexible "slow path" way for injecting malicious traffic by a malicious process (see "Malicious addition on the slow path" in the figure) running in one of the namespaces. This process could be simple, e.g., a python script that has access to the virtual interfaces of emulated FRER channels and can inject and/or spoof traffic.

V. CASE STUDIES AND EVALUATION

To validate the utility of our testbed design, we have performed a number of experiments. For all experiments the

Fig. 1. Testbed overview

following settings have been applied:

- The Talker process sends UDP packets to the Listener process.
- Both FRER channels are configured to have 100 ms delay, 20 ms jitter and 5% drop rate.
- We have recorded all traffic before the Replication function and after the Elimination function. In this way we can analyse the effect of FRER attacks on the end-to-end performance.

To get a baseline performance for the experiments we recorded some UDP traffic without any malicious additions. In this case FRER was able to compensate the link quality and so the observed packet loss was 0%. We measured the jitter and delay as well as the packet drop in the scenarios where one would assume a change in the metrics (in Subsection V-A, Subsection V-B and Subsection V-D). We found that the only metric showing changes is the packet loss, hence the figures only depict these values. The static nature of the jitter and delay can be explained the performance provided by XDP/eBPF.

A. Random tamper attack

We have performed an experiment in which the attacker changes the sequence number of a given percentage of packets on one of the two FRER channels. Note that only one of the channels is compromised in this scenario. Considering the properties of the channel, we anticipate the overall packet loss to exceed 50%. The results confirm this expectation as we can see it on Fig. 2. Additionally, it is worth noting that each intensity level experiment was repeated 10 times to ensure statistical significance.

In this attack method, the malicious actor does not gather information about the state of the system; instead, it randomly modifies the sequence numbers in the FRER R-TAGs.

Despite its simplicity, random tampering can severely disrupt data streams. When employing two FRER channels, if an attacker alters the sequence number of a packet and it coincidentally gets lost on the other channel, sequence numbering desynchronization occurs due to the lack of retransmission or synchronization mechanisms. In our study, with tamper intensities of 40% and 70%, desynchronization occurred 6 times out of 25 runs and 12 times out of 25 runs, respectively.

B. Next sequence attack

The next sequence attack closely resembles the random tamper attack described in Subsection V-A. In this experiment, the attacker changes the sequence number of a certain percentage of packets on one of the two FRER channels to the next valid sequence number. This scenario (as can be seen on Fig. 3) yields results very similar to the random tamper attack. The deviation here is much smaller however. This can be explained by the fact that the sequence numbers are systematically increased by only one value. If the attacker chose to alter not only the sequence numbers, but the data itself then that would have been accepted as well, hence the percentage of lost packets on Fig. 3 can be interpreted as the percentage of falsified data as well.

C. Late packets

Throughout our work we have performed an experiment where attackers eavesdrop on network traffic and send packets with existing sequence numbers, which ideally should trigger a latent error, as discussed in Subsection III-B. However, our FRER implementation lacks this feature, so the testbed simply discards late packets. We acknowledge this limitation but believe it could be addressed given the testbed's extensibility. Notably, [3] specifies error generation but not upper-layer responses, suggesting that the recorded traffic remains useful for analysis. Handling more complex cases would likely require custom code regardless.

D. Path manipulation

To assess the behavior of our testbed in a scenario where an attacker reconfigures the network to route all redundant packets through a single FRER channel instead of two, we conducted the following experiment: We maliciously modified the fast path to broadcast packets on one channel only and duplicated all traffic on the slow path, mirroring the scenario in Subsection V-D. Results demonstrate that the percentage of lost packets correlates with link configuration; for example, configuring a link with a 5% packet drop rate yields a similar loss percentage.

VI. RELATED WORK

Security considerations of FRER — and Time-Sensitive Networking in general — are widely studied in the literature. Authors of [7] evaluate different threat vectors using

Fig. 2. Impact of the random tamper attack

Fig. 3. Impact of the next sequence attack

the STRIDE [10] methodology, and point out the limitations of current solutions. Furthermore, [11] provides a broader overview of TSN-related security issues by exploring potential attacks against different protocols, including FRER.

Creating a TSN testbed is imperative for well-founded research. TSN-FlexTest [1] builds a testbed using generic commodity hardware and open-source software components to enable flexible TSN measurements. TSN-FlexTest provides insights into the behaviour of different network stream patterns in a single TSN switch. TSimNet [12] is a simulation framework based on OMNeT++. It incorporates all non-time-based features of TSN in a modular and extensible manner.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we designed a lightweight security testbed for the FRER protocol. We created the testbed leveraging openly available technologies with simplicity and flexibility in mind. Reliance on mainstream technologies ensures a lower entry barrier and makes it easy to modify the behaviour of the system. Network characteristics, such as loss, delay and jitter are also configurable using well-known tools. It can run on a single machine and provides a high level of portability thanks to the underlying eBPF implementation.

Furthermore, we presented three attack vectors and demonstrated their effect through four case studies using our testbed. We demonstrate that our design can accommodate attacks with strict timing requirements. To inspire further security research, we made our testbed and the presented attack scenarios publicly available.

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